

How Does Feeling Appreciated Enhance Educational Institutional Performance?

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ABSTRACT: Job equalisation is considered a bureaucratic simplification to make it more agile and dynamic. It turns out that for some functional officials, this process has progressed beyond the normal process. The purpose of this study is to explore how human resources in educational organisations undergoing job equalisation still feel valued and appreciated.

In this study, a naturalistic qualitative paradigm was used, combined with a descriptive approach. This approach was chosen because of its perceived ability to understand social phenomena, particularly sequences of events, from an internal perspective. Face-to-face interviews and several direct WhatsApp messages were used to collect primary data from seven informants. As the study findings indicate, organisational policies have not prioritised the development of human resources or granted job equality. The budget for human resource self-development has not yet demonstrated the impact of job equalisation. After the job equalisation process is complete, they are still recognised for their efforts in their previous work rhythms and not yet in their new positions.

KEYWORDS: Appreciation, educational institution, feeling, organisational performance, organisational support

INTRODUCTION

In the current era of digitalisation, there is a transition from human resource development to human capital development; therefore, it is essential to prepare dependable human resources[1, 2]. In other words, the potential of human resources is essentially one of the basic capitals in an organisation, where human resources are the implementers of activities in the organisation, who have an essential role in achieving organisational goals[3, 4]. Humans must alter their activities and even contend with global unpredictability. Humans must be able to predict a progressive future by responding to these changes comprehensively and integratively. The response of human resources in the organisation to all changes cannot be separated from the organisation's gratitude and appreciation, so that positive employee behaviour will be seen and formed[5]. Employees with high productivity will be in a healthy and safe workplace with access to the information they need to do their jobs. Therefore, according to Porter, the workplace must develop the learning abilities of its employees to provide added value to the organisation and gain a competitive advantage[6].

In educational institutions, including the State Islamic University of Sultan Aji Muhammad Idris Samarinda (UINSI Samarinda), two types of human resources will be discovered: lecturers and education professionals. They have their respective duties and functions to improve higher education performance. Both lecturers and education employees are emotional beings. It was common to associate empathy with a person's emotions. When we agreed that empathy is a psychological emotion[7], everyone can experience it in work and social relationships. The bureaucratic simplification policy for educational staff made their feelings a little bit rise because they have worked for more than ten years and have held echelon 4 positions with a work rhythm that they understand well. Therefore, the organisation must create conditions that encourage employees to be more attached to their work because the performance of its employees determines the success or decline of an organisation. In other words, organisations must be able to manage human resources properly[8], this creates an organisational culture and climate that is perceived as supportive and friendly by employees. Their salary goes up, but they don't have competence in the new functions they carry out. They worry about their ability to put forth energy, courage, and the ability to survive in the face of work difficulties, and the seriousness of work decreases because they are still working on their old job and cannot focus on increasing competence for their new position even though equalisation is intended to support welfare or income adjustments, as well as the employee career development system[9]. Feelings that arise in response to being recognised, acknowledged, or valued by another individual[10] is a construct of gratitude that has

become a problem for educational staff. On the one hand, they are appreciated by the state with higher functional allowances. Still, on the other hand, the results of the equalisation have prevented them from experiencing a change in work rhythm because they lack the competency to perform their actual functional positions. Ultimately, how those in Islamic higher education institutions can appreciate simple pleasures and the contributions of others to the institution's advancement is essential for further discussion.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Organisational Citizenship Behaviour

Successful organisations require organisational members who will go above and beyond regular responsibilities to deliver results that exceed expectations [11–14]. Organisations are desperate for personnel who can demonstrate good organisational citizenship conduct. This necessitates what we refer to as commitment—a strong psychological bond between the employee and the company. It typically results from favourable sentiments or emotions associated with the work, which are impacted by a variety of work-related elements, including pay, benefits, recognition, the task itself, and connections with superiors and coworkers [15].

One of the new work behaviour concepts is organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB), which has five dimensions [16–18]:

- a. Altruism is the habit of helping other employees without coercion on tasks that are strongly related to various organisational operations.
- b. Consciousness, which includes performance and role requirements that surpass the minimal norms.
- c. Civic Virtue, demonstrate voluntary participation in and support of organisational functions on both a professional and social level.
- d. Sportsmanship is about breaking taboos and causing negative issues even when annoyed.
- e. Courtesy is the act of assisting others with work-related problems.

According to Ismainar's research from 2015, companies play a significant role in providing workers with socio-emotional requirements like respect, care, and tangible rewards like pay and health insurance. Fulfilling employees' demands for approval, admiration, and affiliation is facilitated by making them feel valued by the firm. Organisational support yields positive outcomes for both the organisation and its employees. Favourable evaluations from the organisation also boost confidence that more effort at work will be appreciated, so that employees will pay more attention to the appreciation received from their superiors [19]. To put it another way, organisational culture and leadership are prerequisites for members of the organisation to demonstrate OCB [20].

B. Leadership

Leaders are individuals who hold significant influence over an organisation's future. When an organisation successfully performs its tasks and achieves its goals, the leader is regarded as successful and demonstrates effective leadership. The leader is the one who inspires and encourages workers, makes accommodations for their skills and development goals, and helps them satisfy their needs while they're at work. Employees feel fortunate to be employed by the organisation because of this. A successful and effective leader can inspire and motivate people by setting a positive example [21]. They are empathetic as well. Empathy is the ability to understand how other people feel, perceive things from their perspective, and experience ourselves in their shoes [7]. Empathic involvement was discovered in the classroom, a valuable skill that may be taught to elementary school pupils at a young age to promote a respectful attitude toward others [22] and among health workers [23]. Compassionate leadership significantly impacts employee behaviour because it is comforting and fosters a sense of self-worth and the capacity to overcome obstacles. Numerous studies attest to the value of empathy in the workplace and in producing the degree of optimism and self-assurance that employees require when working through challenging times [24].

In 2017, Dale Carnegie conducted a study called "Corporate Culture," which found that organisational culture fosters worker engagement and productivity [25]. Building strengths among employees, addressing imbalances more frequently than penalising them, and placing pressure on their vitality and growth will all contribute to a positive workplace atmosphere and increase employee engagement [26]. According to a 2017 Gallup survey, only 15% of workers in 155 countries feel engaged, and those who are openly frustrated that their needs are not being satisfied. Although workers who are engaged with the organisation and their work would benefit from it, as was the case with the PT BTN Pekanbaru branch office staff [27].

C. Taken Aback of Employee

All educators who received equalisation were taken aback for the first time. They are experiencing culture shock [28]. Even though they had learned about the policy through multiple means of communication, they were nevertheless taken aback. They are still working on their prior job while being confused about their new responsibilities, which impacts their organisational citizenship behaviour. At the same time, management has not demonstrated a policy that sympathises with the shift in their standing six months after the first inauguration. Even though we are aware that the organisation's human resources, career development, and resources are crucial to pay attention to—both by the leadership and the workforce—fighting for it is synonymous with fighting for the advancement of the organisation, and ignoring it is synonymous with neglecting and ignoring the organisation [29].

The "good citizens" phenomenon is central to the logic behind the formation of Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB). A good citizen engages in social activities, votes, and assists their neighbours. Stated differently, an individual who does voluntary acts that enhance the welfare of the community [30]. OCB is an attitude shown by an individual in productivity outside of their responsibilities. It is interpreted as the willingness to cooperate, which is an essential factor in achieving organisational goals with five dimensions.

In this study, we will examine and describe the human as an organisational resource, particularly in an educational institution (State Islamic University of Sultan Aji Muhammad Idris Samarinda), undergoing a bureaucratic simplification policy implemented by the Ministry of Empowerment of State Apparatus and bureaucratic reform (Kemen Pan-RB). The study will capture how they act and whether they continue adding value to the organisation once confronted with the irregularities in post-equality careers. Even though we know that loyal workers tend to exhibit higher productivity [20].

THEORY/CONCEPT

The theory used to analyse this research is the theory of perceived organisational support (POS). This theory assumes that to determine the organisation's willingness to recognise efforts at work and meet socio-emotional needs, employees develop global beliefs about the extent to which the organisation is willing to value their contributions and care about their well-being, as well as meet socio-economic needs. This belief is essential for employees to have that their organisation values their efforts and cares about their well-being. Perceived organisational support (POS) can be realised when an employee believes that their organisation provides the necessary resources, or even additional resources, so that they can carry out their functions efficiently and effectively. This theory also explains that employees tend to attribute human qualities and characteristics to their organisation. POS contributes to the development and efficiency of the organisation, and is also influenced by several aspects related to employee interpretation of motivation, such as increased practical commitment, trust, and performance for the organisation and for its employees, such as increased job satisfaction and decreased stress[31].

RESEARCH METHODS

The qualitative naturalistic paradigm with descriptive methodologies is said to be capable of understanding social phenomena from an inside perspective, particularly the process of occurrences [32]. Making facts and phenomena easy to comprehend and gaining a thorough grasp is the primary objective[33]. As shown in Table 1, the 14 public workers or education people who have experienced equalisation into specific functional roles at UINSI Samarinda. Primary data were received purposefully [34] from 7 informants, four female and three male, through face-to-face interviews and personal messages on WhatsApp for more information, most of which came from archivists, one from a financial management analyst, and a young expert in public relations. Because eight archivists comprise the sum of the 14 equalised structural jobs, functional positions corresponding to archivists are likelier to be informants.

Table 1. Data on specific functional equalisation results in 2020-2021

<i>Name</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Position Before Equalisation</i>	<i>Position After Equalisation</i>
Employee 1	F	Head of the academic subsection of Faculty 1	Young Expert in Archiving
Employee 2	F	Head of the general subsection of the research and community service unit	Young Expert in Archiving

Employee 3	M	Head of the university general subsection	Young Expert in Archiving
Employee 4	M	Head of the general subsection of Faculty 1	Young Expert in Archiving
Employee 5	F	Head of the academic subsection of Faculty 2	Young Expert in Archiving
Employee 6	M	Head of the general subsection of Faculty 3	Young Expert in Archiving
Employee 7	F	Head of the general subsection of Faculty 2	Young Expert in Archiving
Employee 8	M	Head of planning and finance	Associate Planner
Employee 9	M	Head of planning sub-section	Financial management analyst
Employee 10	M	Head of the sub-section of finance	Financial management analyst
Employee 11	M	Head of the general subsection of Faculty 4	Young Expert of Public Relations
Employee 12	M	Head of the university's academic subsection	Young Expert in Learning Technology Developer
Employee 13	F	Head of the academic subsection of Faculty 4	Young Expert in Archiving
Employee 14	M	Head of the general department of the university	Associate Management of Procurement of Goods and Services

Source: Documentation of Research from the Institution

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Budget Support for Change

If the University of Malang pays closer attention to the requirements of its faculty to retain its finest faculty members[35], the study's findings revealed that organisational policies have not yet concentrated on creating human resources for equalisation positions. The budget that encourages human resource self-development through equivalency positions has not received a budget portion in line with the spirit of equivalency in the 2021 fiscal year. Even though the first inauguration occurred at the end of 2020. After completing the equalisation process, they receive little acknowledgement for their efforts.

An educational institution where they work is still focused on strengthening the competency of lecturers in various study programs. As human resources, lecturers play an essential part in the accreditation process for institutions and study programs. On the other hand, educational staff have not received more attention for their contribution to the development of the institution. Naturally, this isn't in line with the justice component of perceived organisational support, which requires organisations to have equitable policies for allocating resources to staff members, because fairness will impact providing all employees with safe and comfortable working environments[36].

In the 2022 fiscal year, organisational recognition began in the form of budget availability for basic training, but it was not able to cover all employees who participated. Some still had to cover operational costs for attending off-site training, as stated by employee 5 in Bali in October 2022.

"The available funds at the faculty are not sufficient to send two employees in the same year" (interview with employee 5).

Meanwhile, in the 2023 fiscal year, budgetary support from the institution began for offline and paid training. Nine archivists participated in training at the Gadjah Mada University Archives in Yogyakarta in July 2023. In 2024, the institution provided support for training at the archivist training centres at the National Archives and in Bandung, as well as at the Ministry of

Communication and Information Technology Training Centre for public relations positions. Meanwhile, in 2025, one archivist and two other archivists participated in archival training in Solo in August and in Yogyakarta in October 2025.

There are two types of financing methods available: free of charge, because the list of names is included in state funding, and paid if the name is not on the list. For the functional position of a financial manager, sufficient training is provided by the supervisory agency. According to Employee 9, their frequent absence from both offline and online training was due to the busy schedule in the finance department and the lack of coordination among similar functional positions. Employee 11, meanwhile, stated that the organisation is quite supportive of employees developing their competencies, especially if the training is free and conducted online. However, if it is conducted offline, the budget is limited. However, career development requires training appropriate to their functional positions, especially for archivists, as they currently have additional duties as heads of administrative, household, and state-owned enterprises (BMN) work teams, as well as heads of academic and student affairs work teams.

B. Appropriate training for the right career path

While public relations officers received promotions in their fourth year, all archivists on the path to equalisation had not experienced significant career advancement. They behaved in ways that exceeded the organisation's expectations, endured less-than-ideal circumstances, and continued to be accountable to their previous job descriptions. They had strived to behave well within the company as members. As a result, they believed this indicated they were being treated as second-class members of the organisation. At the same time, the self-esteem of those occupying similar functional roles outside the organisation was also lower. They believed they lacked the same knowledge of the job descriptions required for their positions, although this also impacted the institution's credibility. Cultural values and campus terminology regarding professionalism can be demonstrated through competency. However, without intervention to make them competent in their functional roles that lead to equalisation, the best results cannot be achieved. Their commitment may not be the same as before. This aligns with research at Bank Bukopin, where organisational culture did not contribute to employee performance, but employee commitment was what led to continued better performance[37].

Informants with various equivalent positions stated that the educational institutions where they work support them in participating in training to improve their competencies according to their equivalent positions, although this is still limited if the training requires a budget. However, according to research conducted by Widjajani in 2014[38], it was stated that employees who have high organisation-based self-esteem will produce ideal behaviour that exceeds organisational expectations because they will believe in themselves and be proud to be part of the organisation. Therefore, institutions should also make efforts to increase the self-confidence of their employees so that they can make greater contributions to the company. These initiatives include creating policies that encourage functional staff members to pursue equity in their career trajectories. Although they are not health workers and have no intention of leaving their jobs [39], feeling appreciated by employees is one component to reduce burnout with additional tasks, so that employees love their jobs and the salaries they receive more.

For educational staff who experienced functional equalisation, the conditions of shock they experienced with the institutional response they received for their career development had nothing to do with the length of service dimension to become a good citizen in the organisation, even though all of them had worked for more than ten years. This is similar to one of the research findings at PT. Garuda Indonesia Airline Tbk where being a good citizen in the organisation was not due to the length of service in the organisation [40]. As human beings with emotions, the government's breakthrough in equalising echelons for certain functional positions initially shocked them. They had to learn something new, which naturally required more energy and organisational support. According to a study conducted at PT Bumi Pembangunan Pertiwi Madiun, workers who receive career development and care will have an impact on companies that employ a large number of Indonesian citizens[41]. This means that leaders must create meaningful work, offer growth opportunities, and ensure a safe and healthy work environment to humanise work, because it is the leader who is first and foremost responsible for appreciating employees[42].

The findings of this study are inconsistent with one indicator of job satisfaction, namely, promotions [43], which serves as an effort to motivate them to work. If there are no available positions, their performance regarding career development will not improve, as experienced by archivists. In fact, their performance may decline in the future due to a fading sense of gratitude that arises in response to a lack of recognition, acknowledgement, or appreciation from others [10]. Employees who demonstrate OCB behaviour will grow into excellent organisational citizens, which translates into high-calibre service. Two main factors

that influence the improvement of OCB behaviour outside the organisation are internal factors originating from employee satisfaction, morale, positive attitudes, and so on, and external factors originating from outside the employee, such as company culture, leadership style, and management systems [44]. In this study, the internal cause, namely the lack of job satisfaction, is caused by external factors in the organisational management system, which is responsible for the decline in employee citizenship who underwent echelon equalisation. Therefore, the higher education institution, namely UINSI Samarinda, must understand the factors that cause the re-emergence of OCB in its educational staff who underwent echelon equalisation and still received additional tasks as a work team with duties similar to their positions before the equalisation, so that ultimately employees achieve better citizenship and contribute according to the dimensions that form the ideal OCB. One way that institutional leaders can understand the feelings of employees with equalisation positions is through internal communication [31, 45]. This must be done continuously to obtain employee feedback for the development of a more positive workplace culture.

CONCLUSION

Because they have to compete with some functional positions that are not equalised at the same level, the five dimensions of OCB decrease after the abnormal position equalisation procedure. If a resolution is not discovered, organisational operations may be disrupted. Not enforcing any regulation as if nothing had happened is not a solution, even though it is improbable that they will relocate or choose to retire early from their place of employment, as has happened in private companies. Institutional leaders need to increase the empathetic involvement of members of the equalisation team by providing funding for their professional development, since they are human resources with the same rights as other human resources in the organisation. Effective leaders have the guts to take chances, recognise and reward those who succeed, and move their teams closer to shared objectives. If all executives support it, organisational performance will rise.

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